

Appendix: Reproducibility Challenge Artifact and reports

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this report is to reproduce the results presented in the paper "Data Flow Lifecycles for Optimizing Workflow Coordination (DataLife)". DataLife illustrates how to use directed acyclic graph (DAGs) to describe the flow of the data and tasks in the scientific workflows, which can provide an insightful suggestion to further optimize the workflow through better task and data placement. This paper presents a method to analyze data flow lifecycles and offer methods to reduce data movement for improved performance. To use DataLife, the steps can be outlined as follow:

- 1) **Monitoring:** DataLife tool suites provide a library for monitoring the necessary I/O executions, which can override the original I/O calls using LD_PRELOAD. They also provide a wrapper `datalife-run` that can be used.
- 2) **Graph Construction:** From the I/O histogram output, the DFL graphs can be constructed accordingly.
- 3) **Analysis:** We can observe the pattern appeared in the DFL graphs and use the suggestion associated to each of data patterns to optimize the workflow, this may include co-scheduling, caching, anticipatory data movement.

This report aims at reproducing the followings:

- 1) Ranked table of composite edge (Figure 2f in the original paper)
- 2) DFL caterpillar graph (Figure 4a in the original paper)
- 3) Execution time for each configurations of the optimized workflow (Figure 6 in the original paper)

II. HARDWARE SETUP AND SYSTEM ENVIRONMENT

Hardware used for this reproducibility report includes:

- Number of Nodes: 3
- CPU: Dual AMD EPYC 9654 96-Core Processor
- PCI: ConnectX-7
- Disk: Supermicro (Samsung) 3.84TB U.2 PM9A3 NVMe. 6.8 GBps Read / 4.1 GBps Write
- OS: Ubuntu 22.04
- Job Scheduler: SLURM

We use NFS for the shared file system across the 3 nodes.

III. SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENT

A. Software Overview

The compiler used are GNU GCC 13.2.0 for DataLife and 1000 genome, and GNU GCC 9.5 for Montage. We follow and adapt the code in **DataLife** GitHub, which contains:

- `flow-monitor` - a tool for monitoring I/O to obtain the I/O histogram data.
- `flow-analysis` - a python library for generating all DFL graphs.

- `tutorial` - example run commands for the results presented in the original paper. We modify the `slurm` scripts to fit our hardware setup of 3 nodes. The modified scripts can be found in the artifacts.

B. Challenges faced and Issues

1) *Scaling:* In the paper, 10 and 15 nodes were used to evaluate the performance of the optimized workflow. The optimized workflow used 10 chromosomes as inputs, which are distributed across the 10 nodes. In our experiment, we scale down the chromosomes to 6 to be suitable for our cluster of 3 nodes.

2) *Installation of monitoring library:* Since the main repository is still developing for supporting more file extensions, example scripts, it lacks the CI/CD for testing. We found that the latest commit (85dde76) has an error during compilation. We document our fixes in the C section.

3) *Incomplete I/O output for some file extension:* The **DataLife** monitoring tool is unable to capture some of the I/O calls to some file extensions when the file format is not supported. Moreover, when running the commands from the example scripts provided:

```
./mutation_overlap.py -c 1 -pop SAS
```

that takes SAS as an input file, the monitoring tool is unable capture the I/O calls to SAS file. We fix this issue by copying SAS to `SAS.txt`. Likewise, this fix will also be required for AFR, ALL, AMR, EAS, EUR, GBR. Hence, when using **DataLife** monitoring tool for other workflow, user have to ensure that the file extension is supported. Otherwise, the I/O histogram results will be incorrect as some of the file traces will not be included.

4) *Reproducibility differences:* We explored different number of nodes as well as different storage options. As we only had 3 nodes, we tried to compare between 2 and 3 nodes, as well as with `ssd/shm` environments with staging. When we plotted our reproduced evaluation table 3, it is also slightly different from the ones in the paper. In the paper, 10 nodes with the optimizations proposed with the `datalife` analysis can outperform 15 nodes. Since we only had 3 nodes, we tried to simulate this with 2 nodes. However, 2 nodes was still does not outperform 3 nodes.

C. Installation of DataLife monitoring tool and example usage

We compile the latest DataLife monitoring tool (in `flow-analysis` directory) with GCC 12.3.0. From the latest commit (85dde76), there is an undefined variable `_STAT_VER` in line 554 of `srcLib.cpp`. We need to manually define the `_STAT_VER` variable or define the variable through `make` command with `-D` flag for the compilation to

be successful. With older versions of the DataLife, there will not be any compile errors.

After the compilation, there will be file: `datalife-run` and `libmonitor.so`. Both files can be used to monitor the I/O calls. The example usage is as follows:

- **datalife-run:**

```
datalife-run <application.sh>
<application-args>
```

e.g.

```
datalife-run individuals.py
ALL.chr1.250000.vcf 1 29 30 30
```

- **libmonitor.so:**

```
LD_PRELOAD=libmonitor.so
<application.sh> <application-args>
```

e.g.

```
LD_PRELOAD=libmonitor.so
individuals.py ALL.chr1.250000.vcf 1
29 30 30
```

D. 1000 Genome workflow

We adapt the sample workflow scripts for obtaining I/O statistics from `datalife/tutorials/evaluation_scripts/performance/1000genome_plot/1000genome_per_f_number/data_collection.sh` by attaching the `LD_PRELOAD` before each task script and rerouting the `*_stat` files generated to a separate folder for each task. To find out what parameters we should run for the 1000 genome workflow, we looked at the `workflow.yml` file and followed the workflow. This can be seen in `data_collection.sh`.

The directory of the final I/O histogram data should be in the following format:

```
1000genome_input/
- frequency_ALL_ID16/
  - ALL.txt_424642_r_stat
  - ALL.txt_424642_r_trace_stat
  - ALL.txt_424642_w_stat
  - ALL.txt_424642_w_trace_stat
  ...
- frequency_AMR_ID17/
  - AMR.txt_424711_r_stat
  - AMR.txt_424711_r_trace_stat
  - AMR.txt_424711_w_stat
  - AMR.txt_424711_w_trace_stat
  ...
```

After we obtain the I/O statistics file, we need to clean the file names. For example we need to rename it to

```
1000genome_input/
- frequency_ALL_ID16/
  - ALL.txt_r_stat
  - ALL.txt_r_trace_stat
  - ALL.txt_w_stat
  - ALL.txt_w_trace_stat
  ...
```

```
- frequency_AMR_ID17/
  - AMR.txt_r_stat
  - AMR.txt_r_trace_stat
  - AMR.txt_w_stat
  - AMR.txt_w_trace_stat
  ...
```

This is because the numbers refer to the process id that is running. But when plotting the graph, it needs to track the same file trace. For instance, given a workflow $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$, when monitoring $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow C$, B will have different process ids. Hence why we need to remove the process id from the name such that it is referring to the same flow. We will have to do this for all of the files that are being monitored. We can then put that into the right folder, in this case the `1000genome_inputs` folder.

After that, we can directly plot the graph through the library of flow-analysis in the **DataLife** repository. The command to generate the DFL graphs is

```
python scripts/1000genome_dfl.py \
-task <dflg-ctree/tree/ranking>
```

The result of the ranked list table IV shows the data volume of each vertice and sort by data volume, this can be used to identify the data file and task to be optimized, which includes: co-scheduling, task-data placement. We notice that the vertices between `ALL.chr1..._annotaion.vcf` and `sift` task contains huge amount of data flow. However, since this is a single task with one large input data, the workflow cannot be optimized much from this insight. Hence, we shift the focus on to the next individual tasks.

The DFL-caterpillar graph (1) shows a large bar of sifting task (red) that consume the file `ALL.chr1..._annotaion.vcf`. As previously mentioned, there is no improvement opportunity in this region. Hence, we filter the `sift` task out and reran the DFL-caterpillar graph generation scripts. From 2, we can observe the *inter-task data locality* pattern as defined in **Table 1** of the original paper. This suggest we can optimize the workflow by co-scheduling the `individuals` tasks, and caching. We modify the SLURM script for co-scheduling across 3 nodes and staging in RAM (`/dev/shm`) before the execution of each `individuals` tasks. The full scripts can be found in the same artifacts.

Note: the DFL caterpillar graph we obtain and the caterpillar graph appeared in the paper is different as the *sifting* task take more execution time than *merge* task (depends on hardware setup). Hence, the critical path is instead `ALL.chr1.phase3..._annotation.vcf` \rightarrow *sifting* \rightarrow *sifted.SIFT.chr1.txt* \rightarrow *frequency*. If the execution time is the opposite, we will obtain the same graph as in the original paper.

Next, we will illustrate the improvement of the optimized workflow from DataLife suggestion over the original run. From the SLURM scripts with co-scheduling and caching in `/dev/shm`. We then plot the performance of each configura-

tion in Figure 3. The

E. Additional: Montage

For the additional application for the Reproducibility Challenge, we are tasked to explore potential performance optimizations for the Montage workflow using dataflow. We tried to compile Montage and run it but ran across a few issues.

1) *Versioning errors:* In the `Repro_Challenge_SC24_Additional_App-Montage.pdf` given, the instructions wrote that we just needed to install Montage of version 5.0 or higher. We tried the running with Montage 6.0 tarball, but it will give an error when the pictures overlap in the `mDiffFit` stage. Instead of indicating the dimensions of the overlap, it will indicate “Blank Image”. We also tried using the git tag `v6.1`, which should be the same as the 6.0 tarball, in the case that the source code is the error, but it still resolved to the same error. This was resolved by cloning the current HEAD of the Montage source code, the commit hash is `a8bde0`.

2) *Runtime errors:* When trying to run with the given script `montage.sh`, it will be able to run fine until `mImgtbl` and `mAdd`. `mAdd` will use the output of `mImgtbl` to run its task, but the output of the file `(1/2/3)-updated-corrected.tbl` will be empty, causing a `Invalid image metadata file` to be caused in `mAdd`. We verified that this is the same problem in `montage_data_16tasks.tar.gz` as well as `montage_data_32tasks.tar.gz`. Without being able to run the full script, there will not be enough program output traced by DataLife to generate the graphs.

Hence we are unable to run the workflow for Montage.

IV. DELIVERABLES AND FIGURES

Here are the figures and tables that we reproduced from the reproducibility challenge as part of the deliverables.

	producer → data → consumer	Volume
89	ALL.chr1.phase3_shapeit2_..._annotation.vcf → sifting_ID004	39.51GB
71	ALL.chr1.250000.vcf → individuals_ID004	7.62GB
68	ALL.chr1.250000.vcf → individuals_ID001	7.62GB
70	ALL.chr1.250000.vcf → individuals_ID003	7.62GB
69	ALL.chr1.250000.vcf → individuals_ID002	7.62GB

TABLE I

NODE AND EDGE DATA WITH CORRESPONDING VALUES IN GB

Fig. 4. DLFG-Caterpillar

This is the reproduction of the DLFG from the paper.

This is the reproduction of the Table for Figure 2f from the paper.

Fig. 1. Visualizing data volumes with the workflow pipeline

This is the reproduction of Figure 4a from the paper.

Fig. 2. Data volume without sifting

This is the reproduction of Figure 4a from the paper, without sifting.

Fig. 3. Evaluation

This is the reproduction of Figure 6 from the paper.